

MADRAS

D2.3 Printed materials and devices-2

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020-NMBP-TR-IND-2019 GA No. 862492
Project title	Advanced Materials and Processing in Organic Electronics (MADRAS)
Duration of the project	April 2020 - April 2023 (36 months)
WP/Task	WP2
Document due Date	30/11/2021
Actual date of delivery	30/11/2021
Leader of this deliverable	Eurecat
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document status	SUBMITTED

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	18/10/2021	Laura López	Draft version circulated to partners
0.2	09/11/2021	Ignasi Burgués	Inputs from EUT
0.3	12/11/2021	Alassane Sidibe	Inputs from UWL
0.4	30/11/2021	Laura López	Final Document
1.1	08/11/2022	Laura López	Updates from M20 to M27: - Hybridization procedure of MCU on antennas by P&P
1.2	11/11/2022	Ignasi Burgués	Updated from M20 to M27: - Final PAL and HTL for the OPD stack
1.3	11/11/2022	Tomas Syrový	Updated from M20 to M27: -Hybrid ink reformulation. - Highly conductive PEDOT:SWCNT layers development.

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MADRAS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862492 (Art. 29.4)

Executive summary

Deliverable 2.3 comprises a second release of Deliverable 2.1 and exposes advances related to WP2 - T2.1.1. *Development of novel inks printing conditions* and T2.2. *Printed Circuits and SMD assembly*.

Task T2.1.1 aims to set the printing conditions of selected inks developed in WP1 applied to primary active components for the final demonstrators: organic photodetectors and antennas. The partners participating in this task are EUT, GNK, UPA, COC and AWCP.

T2.2 aims to develop the printed circuit hybridization on two cases: 1) placing SMD components and interconnects over antennas printed on nanocellulose foils and 2) assembling photosensor reader printed on PI foil over a polymeric substrate that confers mechanical robustness towards the posterior thermoforming and overmoulding processing.

The participating partners for each case are EUT and UWL for case 1 and TNO for case 2. D2.3 summarizes the most relevant results exposed in D2.1 which entails work carried out from month 5 (T2.1.1) and month 8 (T2.2) to month 12, and reports in more detailed advances first until month 20 (on the planned submission) and with updated information at the end of WP2 in month 27.

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List of abbreviations

Ag NW	Silver nanowires
AWCP	Arjowiggings
CNF	Cellulose Nano-Fibrils
COC	Centrum organické chemie
D:A	Donor:acceptor
ETL	Electron Transport Layer
ETR	eCooltra
EUT	Eurecat
EQE	External Quantum Efficiency
GNK	Genesink
HTL	Hole transport layer
IGZO	Indium gallium zinc oxide
IME	In-mould electronics
INF	InfinityPV
ITO	Indium Tin Oxide
J_d	Dark current
NCF	Nanocellulose foil
NP	Nanoparticles
OLAE	Organic and large area electronics
OPD	Organic photodetector
PAL	Photoactive layer
PCE	Power conversion efficiency
PI	Polyimide
R_s	Sheet resistance
SMD	Surface mount device
TNG	Tecnopackaging
TNO	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research
UHF	Ultra High Frequency
UPA	University of Pardubice
UPS	Ultraviolet Photoelectron Spectroscopy
UWB	Ultra-Wide Frequency
UWL	Uwinloc
WO ₃ or WO _x	Tungsten oxide
WP	Work package

Introduction

MADRAS project aims to demonstrate a materials-driven improvement of OLAE devices, establishing a high-speed manufacturing methodology in a scalable competitive process, which is In Mould Electronics (IME).

Four high performance materials to be developed in MADRAS tackle high cost, instability, and short lifetime of OLAE devices under operational conditions through the development of robust alternatives and innovative approaches.

MADRAS project also addresses the need for innovative and industrial manufacturing processes for the development of robust series of flexible plastronics products. Building on an already established technology as plastic injection will facilitate a faster up-taking.

Developed materials and production process will be validated in two different demonstrators, including a biometric photosensor for user identification and a geotracking flexible tag for the Industry 4.0 sector.

The fingerprint photosensor will be integrated as an IME device in the body part around the dashboard of a scooter from a vehicle sharing company. The integration process will consist in firstly, the attachment of a flexible sensor on a polymer substrate, which will be then thermoformed into the desired shape, and overmoulded with a thermoplastic.

The second demonstrator, a geotracking tag, will consist in a flexible foil based on nanocellulose with a combination of printed antennas (UHF and UWB), a small rigid multipoint control unit part (MCU) and additional SMD components, if necessary. These parts will be integrated into a robust and flexible plastic piece through an overmoulding process. On both demonstrators, the objective of the overmoulding is to add mechanical stiffness and protection to vulnerable sensor and circuit elements.

Purpose of the document

This document presents the advances related to Task *T2.1.1. Development of novel inks printing conditions* and *T2.2. Printed Circuits and SMD assembly* from WP2 from month 12 to month 27.

The objectives reflected in the deliverable are the following:

- To set up the printing processes for selected inks from WP1 by printing techniques such as blade coating, slot die and screen printing. Quality checks are done by optical microscopy, profilometry, contact angle, transmittance, and sheet resistance measurements.
- To continue validating selected photoactive materials to ensure high performance photodetector device (OPD) when applying MADRAS inks.
- To analyse of functionality of the inks (WO_3 , PEDOT:PSS, hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ and Ag NW) on OPD.
- To validate 2nd prototypes of printed antennas including UHF and UWB antennas.
- To evaluate Ag NP with increased adhesion on CNF for antenna development.
- To develop MCU assembly procedure on demo 1 using automated Pick and Place.

Summary of results from Deliverable D2.1

In the first release of deliverable *D2.1 Printed materials and devices-1*, the following results were presented:

1) Reference OPD development:

Prior to the testing of materials from WP1, the search for the most suitable photoactive material system for OPD was thoroughly conducted during the first period of execution of WP2. As a result from a photoactive layer screening study, three D:A blends - PTQ10:Y6, PTQ10:Y12 and PTQ10:IDIC-, were chosen as the preferred candidate systems to be used in MADRAS project.

2) OPD with WO₃:

From M1-M12 two WO₃ inks from GNK formulated for standard and inverted structure, respectively, were tested on organic photovoltaic (OPV) devices, which are built with the same stack as the targeted OPD. A remarkable PCE of 9% was obtained with ink SW41014 (WO₃ S). An experiment to study stability of devices under continuous illumination was performed and revealed photoactivation effect on WO₃-based OPD.

On the contrary, photoactive layer deterioration was detected upon drop casting the WO₃ S ink on top of it. It was argued that this unexpected effect could be due to the presence of an acidic ligand in the ink formulation. Further investigations to elucidate this issue are presented in this deliverable.

3) OPD with PEDOT:PSS:

A set of samples with PEDOT:PSS with different ratio and free of secondary dopants were tested. Although further experiments with well-defined patterned substrates were to be done, promising results were envisaged for the PEDOT:PSS (1:2.5) formulations, which showed the best fill factor in OPV devices. This PEDOT:PSS ratio was tested both on PTQ10:Y12 and PTQ10:IDIC, yielding comparable efficiencies of 3.77% and 3.54%, respectively.

4) Ag NW inks:

Ag NW inks 13 and 23 formulated for slot die were characterized in terms of sheet resistance and optical properties for different layer thicknesses. In addition, the compatibility between the WO₃ and the Ag NWs inks was evaluated by GNK. Ink 13 was selected for further investigation, as it provided the highest conductive films (6-7 Ω/sq sheet resistance) and a transparency as high as 89%.

The Ag NW/WO₃ stack was tested as top electrode/HTL on OPD. However, the IV-curves showed non-reproducible and bad rectifying behaviour compared to reference samples with evaporated Ag/WO₃.

5) Ag NP inks for antenna development:

During the first period, two customized highly conductive Ag NP inks were tested. The chosen ink (S-CS91349) showed a high conductivity around 20 mΩ/sq for a 2.4 μm thick layer, and a good resolution of 100 μm for vertical and 150 μm for horizontal minimum linewidth. The sheet resistance and resolution values obtained fulfil the specifications required for antennas and were further used by UWL for simulations of antennas.

6) Hybridization procedure for geotracking tag

The 1st prototype of UHF antennas was tested by a simple hybridized PCB with a welded UFL connector. Another procedure was tested to further characterize In-moulded prototypes. The procedure consisted in hybridizing interconnecting pads on the front side and access to the antenna from the backside of the CNF foil, where there is no injected plastic. PCBs with UFL are hybridized after injection process on micro-holes filled with conductive paste. More details are explained in D2.2.

7) Hybridization procedure for fingerprint sensor

The hybridization process for Demo 2 was defined as the methodology to transfer the sensor fabricated on polyimide (PI) substrate, onto a plastic substrate suitable for plastic processing. TNO demonstrated that it is possible to integrate a device stack fabricated on PI carrier onto a thermoformable PC substrate, using a thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) as intermediate layer.

The intermediate TPU layer acts as a buffer layer between the PC (which is stretched during thermoforming) and the PI (which can bend but does not allow stretching). Through this material stack, the benefits of the injected PC to PC film adhesion will be kept while still being able to maintain the initial requirement of having the OPD on top of a PI film.

The assembly procedure for demo 2 has been fully described in D2.1, and no additional information has been included in this document.

1. Development of novel inks printing conditions

MADRAS' developed inks are meant to be implemented as transparent conductive electrodes (TCE) and hole transport layers (HTL) in OPD and antennas through different printing techniques. The materials should be applied in the demos as:

- 1) Wox-based inks (neat or hybrid): as HTL in OPD.
- 2) PEDOT-based: as HTL or conductive electrode in OPD.
- 3) Ag NW-based inks: printed circuit on CNF foil for antennas (demo 1) and as TCE in OPD frontplane (demo 2)
- 4) Ag NP-based inks: printed circuit on CNF foil for antennas (demo 1).

1.1 Organic Photodetectors development

The OPD for Demo 2 should fulfil TNO's requirements for fingerprint sensors. These requirements have been updated for visible and near-infrared applications: EQE > 50% (unchanged) and $J_{\text{dark}} \sim 10^{-5} \text{ mA/cm}^2$ (the previous threshold set at 10^{-7} mA/cm^2 is only necessary for x-ray applications). The materials developed in WP1 are meant to be used as solution-processed HTL (WO_3 , PEDOT:PSS or hybrid WO_3 /PEDOT:PSS) and top electrode (Ag NW) in multi-stacked OPD, with the following structure: bottom electrode/ETL/PAL/HTL/top electrode.

Therefore, prior to the testing materials from WP1, the most suitable photoactive materials were judiciously identified. Several combinations of donor polymer with non-fullerene acceptor molecules were studied in lab scale devices, deposited by blade coating on ZnO/ITO substrates. It was agreed that the chosen combination should accomplish three criteria: i) high EQE and low dark current; ii) low performance-thickness dependence; iii) high resistance to temperature.

Although results are already explained in D2.1, we include here an update of Figure showing External Quantum Efficiency (EQE) and power conversion efficiency (PCE) behaviour in relation to the active layer thickness for the different D:A combinations. There was a mistake in the x-axis definition: they were flipped. That has been corrected in Figure 1.

During a significant portion of WP2, the active layer of the OPD devices consisted of blends of PTQ10 (as donor polymer) and IDIC, Y6 or Y12 (as non-fullerene acceptor); these materials were at some point selected to be used in the MADRAS project. These blends demonstrated high efficiency and high enough thickness tolerance (low thickness-performance dependence), which is critical to deliver a homogeneous response in the final fingerprint sensor. Later on, we decided to substitute PTQ10 with PM6 as the donor polymer, owing to the stronger and broader light absorption of PM6. Additionally, we also shifted the non-fullerene acceptor Y6 to DTY6, which shows an identical core structure but significantly higher solubility in non-halogenated solvents, hence allowing a more environmentally friendly processing of the whole active layer.

Figure 1. a) EQE for OPD based on different D:A compositions with structure glass/ITO/ZnO/PAL/MoOx/Ag. b) PCE vs blade coater deposition speed of OPD samples with PAL thickness gradient. c) PCE vs corresponding dry thickness (PAL + ZnO) measured by profilometry.

Figure 2. a) Chemical structures of the donor polymers PTQ10 and PM6, and the non-fullerene acceptors Y6 and DTY6. b) Absorption spectra of the two D:A blends investigated and c) the corresponding EQE spectra; the red dashed line indicates the threshold EQE defined in the project objectives.

1.1.1 WO₃ inks for OPD

The first findings regarding research on WO₃-based inks during this period pointed toward problems of reproducibility of the OPD devices with the three selected PAL systems (PTQ10:IDIC, PTQ10:Y12 and PTQ10:Y6) with the following stack: ITO/ZnO/PAL/WO₃/Ag. The remarkable PCE values obtained during the first period could not be reproduced due to degradation of the developed ink (expiration date 19/05/21). A new batch of ink was sent to Eurecat, although the same issues of chemical attack on the PAL upon drop casting were detected, as well as a too high contact angle (Figure 3).

Figure 3. a) Optical microscopy image showing the chemical attack on the PAL upon drop casting the WO₃ ink. b) High contact angle of the WO₃ ink on top of the PAL indicates a poor wetting behaviour.

Figure 4. (top left) the power conversion efficiency of OPV devices containing the WO₃ HTL (from ink SW41011) (top right) dropped drastically after 5 months of storage. (bottom left) Picture of an OPV device with an intentional PAL thickness gradient, deposited by blade coating at incremental speeds. The device stack is the same as that for OPD: glass/ITO/ZnO/PTQ10:IDIC/WO₃/Ag. (bottom right) Two micrographs showing the formation of crystallites on the PAL after 5 months.

Moreover, the fabricated devices were re-measured after 5 months of storage in inert conditions. As shown in Figure 4, the efficiency dropped drastically. Besides, optical microscopy inspection revealed the formation of crystal structures on the layers, which we attributed to cross-linked derivatives of the acidic binder.

Considering that the efforts to reformulate the WO₃ nanoparticle-based ink without the acidic binder were unsuccessful, a contingency plan was developed: to reformulate the hybrid PEDOT:PSS/WO₃ ink without such acidic binder (see next section).

1.1.2 Hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ ink for OPD.

As opposed to the previously reported WO₃ ink, the hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ ink has been reformulated to exclude the acidic binder. Several iterative ink developments carried out in cooperation between GNK and UPA have addressed the optimisation of surface tension and wettability on the PAL. The following table summarises the best performing inks developed by GNK and their corresponding re-formulations made by UPA.

Ink (GNK)	Ink reformulated (UPA)	Acidic binder
21-152-B	PINK286	YES
21-215-A	PINK287	NO
21-215-B	PINK288	YES

Table 1. Evaluated PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ inks.

Figure 5 shows the comparative performance of OPD including the hybrid HTL made from the different ink batches developed. The statistical data reveal several aspects. First, the reformulation of the inks results in a lower data spreading, which is a direct consequence of the improved wetting behaviour, that allows the complete coverage of the whole device area. Second, such reformulations also yield lower dark current values and higher ON/OFF ratios, comparable with the reference evaporated MoOx HTL.

Figure 5. Statistical data comparing the different developed hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ inks for the deposition of the hole transport layer (HTL) in OPD devices, against the reference evaporated MoOx. A) Dark current at -2 V, b) ON/OFF ratio at -2 V (ON values determined for indoor conditions: 0.2 suns \approx 500 lux). The arrows indicate the change derived from the reformulation of the inks. Full device stack: glass/ITO/ZnO/PTQ10:IDIC/PEDOT:PSS:WO₃/Ag

The *J-V* curves measured in dark conditions of representative devices show a good rectifying behaviour for the three reformulated inks (286, 287, 288) as well as comparable or even lower dark current values with respect from the evaporated MoOx reference device (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Dark J-V characteristics of OPD devices incorporating solution-processed HTL based on the reformulated hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ inks

Amongst the three reformulated inks, PINK287, with no acidic binder that could harm the PAL in the long term, has been selected for further development (see below) and for the fabrication of the OPD on top of the TFT backplane (see D2.5).

The refinement of PINK287 consists of modifications in the ink formulation that enable a better wetting on the PAL and a homogeneous coating. The next hybrid ink version was PINK298. The performance of the OPD devices using this ink was significantly improved, both in terms of the dark current and the ON/OFF ratio (Figure 7). However, this version showed two handicaps: i) a proper wetting on the PAL was only possible by increasing the doctor blade bed temperature up to 90 °C, and ii) WO₃ nanoparticle aggregates were observed as a yellowish precipitate in the ink after a few days.

Figure 7. a) Difference in the average dark current at -2V (top) and ON/OFF ratio (bottom) when replacing PINK287 with PINK298, and b) the corresponding J-V curves. C) problems associated with the new ink PINK298: dewetting is only prevented at high coating temperatures (left), and presence of yellowish aggregates in the ink (right).

PINK313 was the next ink version developed, which included lower boiling point solvents than those in PINK298. This ink resulted in a much faster drying and film formation, which allowed to deposit the layer at 40 °C. However, the wetting on top of the PAL was unsatisfactory, leading to an unsuitable PAL coverage and consequently to higher series resistance and a poorer OPD performance. Then, two more ink iterations were performed to solve the wetting issues. First, a more suitable surface tension was achieved in PINK327, as well as a lower solid content and a faster drying rate in comparison with PINK 298. Lastly, a fine tuning on the solid content was performed in PINK361, which was selected as the final ink version for the HTL deposition in Demo 2 (see OPD performance in D2.5). Noteworthy, PINK361 was validated as a suitable material for the fabrication of Demo 2 by means of up-scaled slot-die coating of the HTL on top of the real size TFT backplane (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Validation of the deposition of PINK361 as HTL on top of the TFT backplane by means of slot-die coating.

Ink #	Primary usage	PEDOT: PSS	Surfactant #	Additional solvents [wt. %]	Ink viscosity [mPa.s] @20 °C 100 s ⁻¹	Ink ST @20 °C	Conductivity [S/cm]	Dry layer thickness [nm]
PINK 298	HTL	21-337-B SW91024	0.1 % ST3+ ST10	----	8.3	31.6	0.26	358
PINK 313	HTL	22-032-E SW91024	0.1 % ST3+ ST10	25	3.9	32.4	0.27	250
PINK 327	HTL	22-032-E SW91024	0.2 % ST3+ ST10	45	2.4	31.5	0.21	128
PINK 361	HTL	22-252-D SW91024	0.2 % ST3+ ST10	15	3.4	30.9	0.22	204

Table 2. Estimated characteristics of hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ PINK ink formulations and its coated layers

For the ink 361 equivalent, a PINK 362 (GenesInk 22-280-A H-SW91024) ink formulation has been prepared. Given ink formulation will be monitored over time for several parameters. For the ink, dry solid content of the liquid portion without the precipitated portion of the ink will be estimated. As an initial dry solid content 2.68 wt. % was estimated. For the layers, the conductivity of the layers (0.21 S/cm) and the UV/VIS absorption spectrum will be measured. This study will be continued in WP2-T4.1. *Upscaling and materials validation process.*

1.1.3 PEDOT:PSS inks for OPD

Following up on the results previously reported in D2.1, the work carried out during M12-20 has targeted the selection of the most suitable PEDOT:PSS ink to be applied on OPD from all the inks formulated by UPA for slot die viscosity range. The printability of such inks on photoactive materials as well as their functionality on OPD has been tested by EUT.

The full description of the developed inks is given in D1.5. In brief, the parameters investigated to tune the rheological properties (viscosity, surface tension), the functionality (conductivity, work function) and the stability of the PEDOT:PSS inks have included: i) solvents, ii) co-solvents and surfactants, iii) secondary dopants, iv) PEDOT:PSS ratio, and v) solid content.

During M12-20 we have worked in narrowing down the selection of PEDOT:PSS inks with the aim of transferring them to the next phase: the fabrication of the fingerprint sensor front plane and OPV with MADRAS's materials. The following two sections summarise the last results on PEDOT:PSS for solution-processed HTL and transparent conductive electrode.

After the M20 month, further optimization of the selected dispersions in the upscaling phase of WP4 took place. In the framework of these activities the properties of the dispersions were further improved, e.g. for PEDOT:PSS 1:1.4 a conductivity of 280 S/cm was achieved with AMIDE I.

1.1.3.1 PEDOT:PSS for HTL

The PEDOT:PSS inks for HTL have been formulated in order to obtain a suitable layer thickness range (50-100 nm) and good hole-transport properties.

In a first stage, the PEDOT:PSS ratio was narrowed down to three different ratios: 1) 1:1.4; 2) 1:2.5; 3) 1:5. It has been systematically observed that the best performing inks were based on the 1:1.4 PEDOT:PSS ratio. As an example, Figure 9 shows comparative J-V curves of OPD using different PEDOT:PSS ratios for the HTL.

Figure 9. Dark J-V characteristics of OPD devices incorporating solution-processed HTL based on the PEDOT:PSS inks of different molar ratios.

For each of the ratios a set of iterations in ink development and testing have been carried by UPA and EUT. The feedback given by EUT in each iteration was implemented by UPA to improve the ink properties of the following iteration. For instance, the progress in ink development for formulations based on the 1:1.4 and 1:5 PEDOT:PSS ratios is presented in Figure 10. As stated above, the modifications of the ink formulation included changes in the solid content and the use and composition of surfactants, co-solvents and secondary dopants (see D1.5 for the complete description of the ink development). For instance, one important learning has been that ethylene glycol works significantly better as a secondary dopant with respect from amide-based dopants.

Figure 10. Statistical data showing the progress with different developed PEDOT:PSS inks for the deposition of the hole transport layer (HTL) in OPD devices, against the reference evaporated MoOx. a) Dark current at -2 V, b) ON/OFF ratio at -2 V (ON values determined for indoor conditions: 0.2 suns \approx 500 lux). Full device stack: glass/ITO/ZnO/PTQ10:IDIC/PEDOT:PSS/Ag.

Throughout this iterative development we have identified the best ink formulation parameters to obtain the desired performance in terms of wetting properties as well as thin film uniformity and functionality. The following table summarises such ink formulation parameters, which correspond to PINK221. The latter yielded in average the lowest dark current values and the highest ON/OFF ratios. The resulting J - V characteristics in OPD devices using PINK221 as the HTL is shown in Figure 11.

Best ink formulation for HTL (PINK221)	
PEDOT:PSS ratio	1:1.4
Secondary dopant	Yes, EG (2%)
Surfactant	Yes, ST3 (0.1%)
Co-solvent	Yes, 2-propanol (33%)
Ink viscosity [mPa.s] @20 °C 100 s ⁻¹	8.4
Charge carrier mobility [cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹]	1.54
Work Function [eV]	4.64

Table 3. Characteristic parameters of chosen PEDOT:PSS ink for HTL.

Figure 11. Dark J-V characteristics of an OPD device incorporating solution-processed HTL based on PEDOT:PSS PINK221 in comparison with the reference evaporated MoO_x.

These results prove the suitability of the developed PEDOT:PSS PINK221 to work efficiently as HTL, as seen in the good rectifying behaviour. Although in this case the dark current values are higher than those obtained with the reference device using evaporated MoO_x, this formulation has been selected to conduct further fine tuning experiments and then be transferred to the development of the OPD devices on the TFT back planes.

1.1.3.2 Highly conductive PEDOT:PSS for transparent electrode

In parallel to the progress in PEDOT:PSS inks for HTL, alternative formulations have been developed to realise fully solution-processed top electrodes with high transparency. Such transparent conductive electrodes (TCE) are intended to be built by combining highly conductive PEDOT:PSS layers with Ag NWs (see next section).

In this case, the best PEDOT:PSS ratio has been identified as 1:2.5 HC, and three optimised formulations have been tested in OPD devices: PINK223, PINK224 and PINK225 (see D1.5). In contrast with the HTL functionality, in this case it has been concluded that the amide derivative used as a secondary dopant results in a better performance highly conductive PEDOT:PSS:

Best ink formulation for highly conductive PEDOT:PSS (PINK224)	
PEDOT:PSS ratio	1:2.5 HC
Secondary dopant	Yes, Amide I (2%)
Surfactant	Yes, ST3 (0.1%)
Co-solvent	Yes, 2-propanol (33%)
Ink viscosity [mPa.s] @20 °C 100 s ⁻¹	16.6
Conductivity [S/cm]	903
Charge carrier mobility [cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹]	1.36
Work Function [eV]	4.41

Table 4. Characteristic parameters of chosen for highly conductive PEDOT:PSS ink.

Figure 12. Dark J-V characteristics of OPD devices incorporating solution-processed HTL based on highly conductive PEDOT:PSS PINK223, PINK224 and PINK225 in comparison with the reference evaporated MoOx.

As seen in Figure 12, the amount of the secondary dopant appears to be critical. The OPD devices containing the highest amount of amide dopant (PINK223, 5% secondary dopant) yielded short-circuited devices. On the other hand, the ethylene glycol dopant (PINK225) didn't perform as good as the amide one (PNK224), as it delivered a significantly higher dark current as well as a poorer rectifying behaviour. Hence, PINK224 has been selected as a highly conductive PEDOT:PSS ink to complement the transparent conductive electrodes based on Ag NWs (see next section).

1.1.3.3 Highly conductive PEDOT:SWCNT layers for transparent electrode

Very promising results of dispersion suitable for semi-transparent conductive layers gave the hybrid polymer where PEDOT is polymerised on the carbon nanotubes (CNT) pre-modified by sulfonated pyrene. System is protected by patent application PCT/CZ2022/050059, "Hybrid composite for preparing thin conductive layers, a method for the preparation thereof, and thin conductive layer prepared from the hybrid composite". In the process, CNT dispersed in the sulfuric acid are modified by pyrene which makes π - π stacking on the surface of CNTs. Pyrene alone is sulfonated during this modification. Product is isolated, excess of sulfuric acid is removed, and it is dispersed in the water and next in situ polymerisation of EDOT is carried out. PEDOT makes ionic pair with sulfonated pyrene fixed on CNTs and all hybrid system is easily dispersed and gives layers with high conductivity higher than 1000 S/cm.

Tests focused on the preparation of printing formulations showed that the layers prepared from the PEDOT/CNT dispersion are too rough and not of sufficient quality. It was found that modification of CNT by substituted pyrene gives mixture easily dispersible which gives smooth layer. This CNT/pyrene system is suitable to be applied in form of coating from bare solution or in the mixture with PEDOT/PSS or PEDOT/CNT system. Preferred substitution of pyrene for CNT modification is sulfonation, direct alkylation by long carbon chain or in the form of amides of long carbon chain like lauryl bonded on the sulphuric or carbon acid of pyrene. System will be up scaled in WP4 and the final printing formulation will be suggested.

Optimised sample of modified SWCNT provide high quality of dispersion. The dispersion of 1190/134 (SWCNT with sulfonation modified pyrene) was improved by addition of 0.1 wt.% ST3 (PINK 367). Layer coated by 60 μ m Bird cube provide sheet resistance 35 Ohm/sq., and transparency $T_{600nm} = 33\%$. When the dispersion was modified by PEDOT:PSS 1:1.4 in ratio 2:1

(PEDOT:PSS:SWCNT) the coating behaviour was even better (PINK 368). Sheet resistance of layer was 45 Ohm/sq, transparency $T_{600nm} = 28\%$ for coated layers was measured. For spiral bar coating modified 1190/134 provide sheet resistance 95 Ohm/sq, conductivity 1220 S/cm and transparency $T_{600nm} = 75\%$. For PINK 368 spiral bar coated layer exhibited sheet resistance 137 Ohm/sq, conductivity 990 S/cm and transparency $T_{600nm} = 73\%$. In summary, objective 1 related to achieving high conductive PEDOT with conductivities up to 500-900 S/cm have been achieved beyond expectations.

Figure 12. PINK 367 coated by 20 μm spiral bar.

Ink #	Wet layer	Primary usage	Basic SWCNT dispersion	PEDOT: PSS	Surfactant #	Ink viscosity [mPa.s] @20 °C 100 s ⁻¹	Sheet resistance [Ohm/sq.]	Transmittance 600 nm [%]	Conductivity [S/cm]
PINK 367	60 μm	TCE	1190/134	----	0.1 % ST3	67.7	35	33	----
PINK 367	20 μm	TCE	1190/134	----	0.1% ST3	67.7	95	75	1220
PINK 368	60 μm	TCE	1190/134	1:1.4	0.1 % ST3	85.3	45	28	----
PINK 368	20 μm	TCE	1190/134	1:1.4	0.1 % ST3	85.3	137	73	990

Table 5. Estimated characteristics of SWCNT/ PEDOT:PSS PINK ink formulations and its coated layers.

1.1.4 Ag NW inks for transparent conductive electrodes

During technical requirements definition it was discussed by consortium that Ag NW inks developed by GNK would be formulated for different viscosity ranges suitable for the different printing techniques used: slot die (20-40 mPa.s) and screen printing (> 1 Pa.s). The inks should be developed with an appropriate mixture of solvents with minimal impact on conductivity.

Regarding transparent conductive inks for slot die, which are meant to be tested as transparent electrode for OPD, GNK has developed very promising inks with enhanced conductivity (down to 5 Ω /sq) and high transparency (> 85%). Besides, the inks show excellent adhesion to scotch test (*scotch 610 3M*) on PET and cellulose foils.

Screen printing would be the technique of choice to print patterned designs on CNF foil. First trials of printability of GNK's customized Ag NW inks on CNF foil have been done with screen printing ink, already developed by GNK.

1.1.4.1 Ag NW inks for slot die

From the inks developed for slot die (see D1.4), INK 13 has demonstrated excellent printability and a good conductivity/transparency balance. Hence, this functional ink has been tested in OPD devices as transparent conductive electrode (TCE).

Initially, the WO_3/Ag NW stack was tested as HTL/TCE in OPD. However, as explained in D2.1, the IV-curves showed non-reproducible and bad rectifying behaviour compared to the reference device with evaporated WO_3/Ag .

It was argued that the observed behaviour could be due to either unwanted electrochemistry between Ag NW and WO_3 or due to percolation of Ag NW into the WO_3 layer. In agreement with this, GNK had observed previously some porosity on WO_3 layers.

In view of these results, alternative HTL/TCE combinations have been explored in order to achieve the target low dark current values. For instance, the addition of a PEDOT:PSS intermediate layer ($\text{WO}_3/\text{PEDOT:PSS}/\text{Ag}$ NW) or the use of new hybrid material PEDOT:PSS: WO_3 could work better. These approaches are yet to be investigated in detail.

Alternatively, a sufficiently thick and homogeneous coating of PEDOT:PSS films could prevent shorts or leakage derived from the percolation of Ag NW towards the PAL and simultaneously provide better function as electron blocking layer.

Therefore, taking the results on highly conductive (HC) PEDOT:PSS inks shown in the previous section, we fabricated fully-solution processed OPD devices (except from the bottom ITO electrode) using combinations of HC-PEDOT:PSS and Ag NWs. We started by comparing again the inks containing ethylene glycol (PINK225) and the amide (PINK224) secondary dopants. Consistently with the previous results, the PINK224/INK 13 combination yielded the most promising results (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Dark J-V characteristics of OPD devices incorporating solution-processed HTL/TCE based on highly conductive PEDOT:PSS PINK224 or PINK225 and Ag NW INK 13, in comparison with the reference evaporated MoO_x . Full device stack: ITO/ZnO/PTQ10:IDIC/PEDOT:PSS/Ag NW.

Since the ethylene glycol proved to give better HTL performance when using evaporated top Ag electrode (see section 1.1.3.1), UPA developed further highly conductive PEDOT:PSS formulations (PINK283, PINK284, PINK285) with modified ratios and surfactant content and composition (see D1.5). However, none of those inks has provided better results than the amide-based PINK224 (Figure 14). In all cases an intermediate HTL layer was included using the well performing PINK221.

Figure 14. Statistical data showing the progress with different developed highly conductive PEDOT:PSS inks combined with Ag NWs for the deposition of the hole transport layer (HTL) and transparent conductive electrode (TCE) in OPD devices, against the reference evaporated MoOx. a) Dark current at -2 V, b) ON/OFF ratio at -2 V (ON values determined for indoor conditions: 0.2 suns \approx 500 lux). Full device stack: glass/ITO/ZnO/PTQ10:IDIC/PEDOT:PSS/HC-PEDOT:PSS/Ag NW.

1.1.4.2 Ag NW inks for screen printing

Two selected Ag NW developed by GNK were sent to EUT for further testing and application. As detailed in D1.4, developed inks were carefully evaluated by GNK in terms of printability, residency time, durability, curing conditions optimization. First trial was done with ink 42. The printing parameters tested at EUT were: screen type: polyester, 355 mesh/inch; squeegee speed: 175 mm/s. And curing conditions: pre-drying (TA for few minutes) + 10 min @ 120°C. Printing test were performed on PET, CNF grade 1, PVDC-coated CNF (P5N). Prints of 1 and 3 layers were compared as shown in Table 6.

Sheet resistance is lower for Ag NW on CNF grade 1 (even lower than on PET). Standard deviation is higher for 1 layer than for 3 layers prints. Haze measurements show different tendency than transmittance. In both cases (with and wo PVDC): haze for 1 layer of Ag NW is lower than the bare substrate or 3 L of Ag NW. This could be attributed to internal scattering from the Ag NW.

Depending on applications, higher or lower optical haze is desired. For photovoltaic applications, transparent paper with high optical haze enhances the path length within solar cell absorbing materials leading to increased absorption.

Substrate	# Ag NW layers	Sheet R (Ω/\square)	Haze (%)	T(%) Integrating sphere @550 nm
CNF grade 1	0	-	75	84.7
CNF grade 1	1	23 ± 6	74.1	81.2
CNF grade 1	3	9.7 ± 0.5	75.3	71.6
P5N PVDC	0	-	72.4	85.9
P5N PVDC	1	31 ± 6	66.2	81.4
P5N PVDC	3	23 ± 2	68.8	72.5
PET (125 μ m)	0	-	0.9	89.4
PET (125 μ m)	1	25 ± 7	-	86.1
PET (125 μ m)	3	15 ± 1	-	81.6

Table 6. Sheet resistance, haze and transmittance characterization for printed layers of ink 42 on different substrates (CNF grade 1, P5N and PET).

Figure 15. Image Ag NW layers (1 or 3) printed on two different substrates (P5N and grade 1).

On a second trial, a new ink (ink 93) was tested and compared with ink 42. The printing parameters tested in this case were: The printing parameters tested at EUT were: screen type:

polyester, 305 mesh/inch; squeegee speed: 175 mm/s. And curing conditions: pre-drying (TA for 90s) + 5 min @ 90°C.

Curing conditions were change according to last findings at GNK. Previous curing conditions at 120°C/5 min was not optimum for the Ink93. GNK obtained better sheet resistance and homogeneities of the sheet resistance when the ink was dried at 90°C (Figure 17 in Deliverable D1.4).

As shown in Table 7, sheet resistance was measured on a 7x7 cm² printed square on different substrates. Prints were done in the same day with the same curing conditions.

Substrate	Ink	# Ag NW layers	Sheet R (Ω/\square)
CNF grade 1	42	2	11.4
CNF grade 1	93	2	17.9
P5N PVDC	42	2	10.5
P5N PVDC	93	2	20
PET (125 μ m)	42	2	10.3
PET (125 μ m)	93	2	20.5

Table 7. Sheet resistance comparison between ink42 and ink 93 printed layers on different substrates (grade 1, P5N and PET).

Figure 16. 100X optical microscopy image of ink 42 and ink 93 layers printed on PET.

Therefore, comparison between Ink42 and Ink93 show that lower sheet resistance can be obtained for ink42. However, ink 42 shows lower residency time and observed degradation of the printed layers after several days. Besides, optical microscopy images were taken showing no critical different in layers appearance.

Final optimization of Ag NW inks for screen printing is still ongoing at GNK but results look promising reaching a transmittance at 550 nm of $86 \pm 3 \%$ with a sheet resistance of $20 \pm 5 \Omega/\square$ for ink 93 (check D1.4 for more detail characterisation).

Ink 42 was tested on OPD/OPV as transparent bottom electrode on CNF foil using MADRAS' developed PEDOT:PSS as HTL and TCE (Figure 17). Devices were not functional, and optimization is ongoing. Work related to the testing of MADRAS materials on flexible substrate is planned for the coming months.

Figure 17. OPD consisting in CNF/AgNW/ZnO/PAL/pink221/pink150/Ag fingers.

1.2 Ag Nanoparticles inks for antenna development

As a recapitulation, consortium agreed to include the development of customized Ag NP ink for the printing of antennas for the geotracking tag due to the electrical: around 100 m Ω /sq sheet resistance.

With experimentally determined values for electrical and dielectric properties of Ag NP printed tracks and CNF foils, UWL performed simulations and delivered prototypes for the printing of antennas (Figure 7). First prototype consisted of a simple structure (at 50 Ω input impedance) to verify some basic parameters and compare with simulations in order to optimise the simulation model. During this period, a second prototype was simulated including UWB antenna, integrated size reduction (fit in a 7x7 cm area), and different “environments” (e.g., the inclusion of TPU layer on top).

Figure 18. UHF (left) and UWB (right) antennas prototypes designs UWL obtained by simulations by UWL. The size of the first prototype of the UHF antenna was reduced to fit injection mould and taking TPU presence under consideration.

Performance validation of both second prototype of antennas was addressed. Firstly, screen with 120T mesh was fabricated. Antennas were printed on CNF foil using selected highly conductive Ag NP ink (S-CS91349). Then they were validated through and hybridized PCB+UF.L SMA connector. As shown in Figure 13, the measured return loss is in good accordance with simulations.

Figure 19. Return loss of 2nd prototype of a) UHF and b) UWB measured at UWL using a connected to RF cable through a U.F.L-SMA adapter.

As previously verified by GNK, Ag NP printed layers shows good adhesion to PET and paper substrates. However, we noticed loose adhesion on CNF substrates. For this period, GNK worked in the optimization of adhesion of Ag NP to CNF substrates by developing a new ink.

Increased adhesion (IA) ink, named CS91367, showed 5B adhesion at the cost of a decrease in conductivity as shown in Table 8. More details on formulation and adhesion tests can be found in Deliverable D1.4.

Ink code	Ink name	Rs (mops)	Thickness (μm)	Resistivity ($\mu\text{Ohm.cm}$)
CS91349	Smart Screen B	22 ± 8	2.3 ± 0.3	4.8 ± 0.8
CS91367	Smart Screen A	130 ± 30	1.7 ± 0.3	20 ± 1

Table 8. Electrical properties for Ag NP-based inks for antenna development.

UWL performed simulations with new ink characteristics, as shown in Table 9.

Ink code	Ink name	Incident Power	Accepted Power	Radiation Power	Radiation efficiency
CS91349	Smart Screen B	1 W / 30 dBm	0.979 W / 29.9 dBm	0.917 W / 29.62 dBm	93%
CS91367	Smart Screen A	1 W / 30 dBm	0.968 W / 29.85 dBm	0.837 W / 29.22 dBm	86%

Table 9. Simulated power and radiation efficiency of the antenna for the two formulated ink.

The simulation on antennas was performed using both formulated inks at the same incident power. Figure 14 shows the distribution of the incident power through an antenna where the reflected power is due to the mismatch of the antenna impedance to the source, the P_{ohmic} is related to the dielectric loss on the substrate and the ink resistivity.

Figure 20. Distribution of the incident power through an antenna.

As shown on the Table 9, the simulated antenna with the improved adhesion ink (CS91367) is less efficient due to its higher resistivity (the accepted power is roughly the same for the both inks). However, UWL concluded that this efficiency is sufficient for a good performance of the demonstration tag, although the lower the resistivity, the better for a competitive Tag.

Performance of both inks on second prototype of antennas was addressed. Antennas were printed on different substrates (PET, CNF ultra 62 g/m² and CNF planarized with PVDC) and cut with a plotter into the shape fitting the chosen mould for plastic injection, as shown in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..** Comparison of performance of both inks has been evaluated in injected samples. Results are presented in D2.6.

Figure 21. UHF and UWB antennas printed on CNF foil (1st row) with two types of Ag NP inks: with high conductivity (ink CS91349) and with increased adhesion to CNF (ink CS91367). Samples are cut with a plotter into the shape fitting specific mould.

2. Printed circuits and SMD assembly

2.1 Printed circuit hybridization on antennas

For this demo, the hybridization process consists in the direct hybridization of UWL's electronic module on the printed foil with the functional antennas. The MCU embeds the harvester chip (for UHF), the microcontroller and the transmission unit (for UWB) and it was agreed that it will be the only hybridized component on the demo. It was discussed that additional sensors will be better optimized if included in the MCU than hybridized on printed foil.

On the final demo, UWL's electronic module should be precisely positioned to get a good complex conjugate matching impedance with the antenna design. The electronic module is a 15 x 15 mm all-in-one board as shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22. 3D model of the UWL's electronic module.

While the complex conjugate is being design with the exact position of the MCU, automated Pick&Place (P&P) procedure has been developed for two cases: i) hybridization of pads on antennas for characterisation and ii) hybridisation of dummy PCBs.

The hybridization procedure is realized at Eurecat with a Puma SMD Pick and Place from Essentec. It consists in 3 main processes:

- 1) Dispensing of conductive adhesive
- 2) Dispensing of structural adhesive
- 3) Pick and Place of the component

Hybridization of SMD contact pads

As shown in Figure 22, the MCU features two differential input pads for the antennas. To do a preliminary characterization of the in-mould antennas, a strategy consisting of in hybridizing pads that connect the two sides of the antennas: the moulded side with the backside of the substrate. The procedure was introduced in *Deliverable 2.2 - 1.2.1 Injection moulding sample preparation* and has been optimized using automatized equipment: an LPKF circuit board plotter for drilling micro-holes and the P&P equipment for adhesives dispensing and placing of SMD contact pads.

As shown in Figure 23, the procedure consisted in:

- 1) Drilling micro-holes on antennas contact pads using a LDKF circuit board plotter.
- 2) Filling of the micro-holes and surrounding with conductive epoxy resin (EPO-TEK H20E) to allow an interconnection from the backside and adhere pads to antennas' footprint.
- 3) Placing of the SMD contact pads using fiducial positioning and curing at 90°C for 1h.
- 4) Application of structural adhesive on pads to reinforce the hybridized pads on the injected side and curing at 90°C for 1 h.

Figure 23. Hybridization procedure for characterization of IM-antennas. Interconnecting pads (d) are hybridized on antenna through perforations (b) using conductive (c) and structural adhesive (e).

In Figure 24, an example of the characterisation strategy used to characterise an in-mould tag with the complex conjugate design before hybridisation of the control unit. For a radiation test of the complex conjugate antenna, a board with matching elements, balun (balanced to unbalanced converter) and connectors was designed so that return loss could be measured through a SMA connector.

Figure 24. Characterisation procedure for in-mould antennas. Antennas with hybridised pads are inject moulded (a), then an external PCB is soldered on pads (b) A balun is soldered on the PCB so characterisation can be performed through a coaxial cable.

Hybridization of dummy PCBs

Once UWL finalized the design of the complex conjugate further development of the hybridization procedure with P&P was carried out. As shown in Figure 25, a fiducial system was included to hybridize a PCB on the defined position on the tag: four 2-mm dots were included in the surroundings of each tag in the screen printing design so the P&P software could read to precisely dispense the adhesives and place of the component.

Figure 25. Altium Designer screenshot of the screen printing tag layout with fiducials (in red) and a schematic of the 15x15mm UMD on top (in violet).

In the case of hybridisation of PCBs, the dispensing of the structural and conductive adhesive on the footprint area is done in the same dispensing step as depicted in Figure 26. Structural adhesive is dispensed on the centre of the area where there are no pads while conductive adhesive (EPO-TEK H20E®) is dispensed on the defined pads: on Pads 8-9 for UWB antenna connection, on pads 10-11 for UHF antenna. See D2.6 for more information about pins definition on MCU.

Figure 26. Structural adhesive dispensation for PCB hybridization.

Regarding structural adhesives, two types of adhesives were tested, one thermal-curable (Structalite® 8805 from Panacol) and another UV-curable adhesive (Loctite 3525AA). The structural adhesive shows a non-homogenous distribution while the UV-curable adhesive spread much smoothly (Figure 27). A less viscous thermal-curable adhesive is pendant to be tested. The use of a thermally curable adhesive is preferred so conductive and structural adhesive are cure at the same time.

Thermally-cured adhesive

UV-cured adhesive

Figure 27. Comparison of the appearance of a glued PCB on top of a printed tag with two different structural adhesives: Thermally and UV cured.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The objectives of this deliverable were first, to report the activities carried out for the setting up the printing conditions for OPD and antennas, main active parts of the two final demonstrators, with material developed in WP1, and secondly, to follow up with the assembly methodology for hybridization of control units on final demo 1. The assembly procedure for demo 2 was already addressed on D2.1. consisting in the transfer of the fingerprint sensor on thermoformable plastic substrate.

Several challenges in the choice of materials for OPD has been identified, being the main one the performance specifications set in D3.1. On this deliverable, requirements for target dark current level on OPD were updated to 10^{-5} mA/cm² at -2V. Dark current levels after applying MADRAS' HTL and printed electrodes were evaluated. At M24, we decided to substitute PTQ10 with PM6 as the donor polymer, owing to the stronger and broader light absorption of PM6, and shifted the non-fullerene acceptor Y6 to DTY6 resulting in the best results in terms of ON/OFF ratio and J_d .

Progress on evaluation of WO₃, PEDOT:PSS and new hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ inks applied on OPD based on chosen D:A combinations is presented in this document.

Regarding WO₃ ink, previously achieved results couldn't be reproduced. Both the devices (containing WO₃ as HTL) and the ink suffered degradation after some months. The degradation was attributed to the presence of an acidic binder of the nanoparticle-based formulation that could attack the photoactive layer. Development of acidic binder-free ink with pristine WO₃ is not possible.

On the contrary, the hybrid PEDOT:PSS:WO₃ ink could be formulated excluding the acidic binder. Hybrid inks with and without acidic binder were formulated by GNK. Preliminary tests of the first batch of inks showed problems of wettability on active layers. Thereafter, surface tension optimization was performed by UPA. The second batch of inks showed an enhanced printability and remarkable results when tested on OPD.

Regarding PEDOT-based inks, PEDOT:PSS ratio was narrowed down to three different ratios: 1) 1:1.4; 2) 1:2.5; 3) 1:5. It has been systematically observed that the best performing inks were based on the 1:1.4 PEDOT:PSS ratio. The feedback given by EUT in each testing was implemented by UPA to improve the ink properties of the following iteration. We have identified the best ink formulation parameters to obtain the desired performance in terms of wetting properties as well as thin film uniformity and functionality. The best ink (PINK221) yielded in average the lowest dark current values and the highest ON/OFF ratios.

A highly conductive ink based on PEDOT:PSS:SWCNT has been developed by UPA giving conductivity of 990-1220 S/cm with transparency of 73-75 %. Hence, objective 1 related to achieving high conductive PEDOT with conductivities up to 500-900 S/cm have been achieved beyond expectations.

On the other side, the highly conductive PINK224 is selected to complement the TCE. This ink was tested in combination with the best Ag NW ink developed in WP1, ink 13. Ink 13 works reasonably well as a TCE when combined with highly conductive PEDOT:PSS ink 224.

Regarding antennas, second prototype of an UHF and UWB antennas were simulated, printed with Ag NP ink and characterized through a simple hybridized PCB with an SMA connector. Both antennas shown good performance in accordance with simulations.

Regarding Ag NW inks for screen printing, 2 optimized inks: Ink42 and Ink93 with good printability were developed and characterized by GNK. Results were checked at EUT and,

MADRAS

although not successful, first trials on the fabrication of OPD on transparent CNF foil were carried out.

On the other side, Ag NP ink with increased adhesion was developed by GNK. Its printability and electrical characteristics were tested, and simulations were performed to evaluate the expected performance using a less conductive ink. It was concluded that performances were good enough for the application but the lower the resistivity, the better for a competitive final tag.

Assembly procedure for the hybridization of connectors or MCU on demo 1 using automated Pick and Place is successfully developed.

4. Risk analysis

The table presented below describes the potential risk and deviations during the project and the contingency plan that would minimize the risk related to the deliverable D2.3.

Risk description	Likelihood	Contingency plan	Who/Actions
Ag NW ink doesn't achieve the expected conductivity and transparency	Medium	Mixture of NW with NPs, curing by different techniques or tuning the thickness of the coating	GNK/Ag NPs based inks were developed for antennas applications (higher conductivity), Ag NW ink coating has been optimized to get the better compromised between transparency and conductivity.
WOx does not achieve the expected conductivity values, mobility and transparency	Medium	Mixture with dopants, curing by different techniques	GNK/ Try to reformulate the WO3 nanoparticle-based ink without the acidic binder. Develop hybrid PEDOT:PSS/WO3 ink without such acidic binder.
New formulations of PEDOT doesn't achieve expected values for hole mobility	Medium	Mixture with dopants and reformulation with different solvents	Nothing to report.
Printed antennas do not show expected impedance / conductivity	Low	Print with alternative nanoparticles inks prepared within the consortium. Use advanced sintering techniques such as photonic and NIR laser curing.	Mitigate since beginning of the project.
Crumpling of the nanocellulose foil during processing, or sensitivity to operational temperature	Medium	Change the solvent of the inks, use laser etching, and alternative curing methods. Work under 150°C	Not detected.
OPD stack with printed electrodes does not reach required dark current and EQE	Medium	Use evaporated HTL and top electrodes for demo 2. HTL and conductive inks developed in MADRAS (PEDOT, hybrid, WO3, AgNW) would then be applied on OPD/OPV.	TNO/ Revise dark current requirements for application in final demo. Chose best HTL/top electrode combination for fingerprint sensor. EUT/ Develop OPD/OPV on flexible substrate using MADRAS' inks and substrates.
Reproducibility of the SMD process	Medium	Redesign of the foil, reallocate the components in the	Nothing to report.

Risk description	Likelihood	Contingency plan	Who/Actions
		optoelectronics -identify the worse scenario and check that the process is still embedding the components.	
Delays in delivery of assets (all)	Low	Day to day coordination of the activities to prevent it	Nothing to report.
Unforeseen conflict between partners (IPR issues, etc) or defaulting party (all)	Low	Build professional working relationships, Signature of Consortium Agreement beforehand, with provision of legal basis for conflict resolutions or /and defaulting mechanisms.	Nothing to report.

Table 10. Risk Analysis